

The Heterogeneous Effects of a Minimum Wage Policy on Hours Worked and Real Wages in Indonesia

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Abstract

This research investigates the heterogeneous effects of the minimum wage policy on hours worked and real wages among low-wage workers in Indonesia. By employing repeated cross-sectional data from the National Labor Force Survey spanning 2020 to 2023, a fully flexible difference in differences (DID) method indicates that the policy resulted in a decrease in average hours worked within the treatment group, while simultaneously increasing real wages. The results demonstrate heterogeneous effects based on economic sector, gender, and region. Across sectors, the impact on hours worked and real wages varies across sectors. Among the 17 sectors analyzed, 8 sectors exhibited significant effects and satisfied the common trend assumption. The analysis by gender shows that women were more prone to experiencing a decrease in hours worked, while men gained more from the rise in real wages. Regionally, the impact of the policy varied between urban and rural workers and evolved over time, reflecting local dynamics in policy acceptance. A robustness test confirmed the consistency and statistical significance of these findings across all model specifications, even with changes in the wage thresholds used to define the treatment and control groups.

Keywords: Fully flexible DID, Hours worked, Low-wage worker, Minimum wage, Real wages

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1. Introduction

A key tension in the labor market exists between workers striving for higher wages and firms focused on reducing labor expenses. Classical economic theory suggests that a perfectly competitive market will reach an equilibrium between labor supply and demand through the marginal product value of labor (Smith, 1776; Borjas, 2024). However, perfectly competitive labor markets are infrequent due to factors such as information asymmetry and institutional complexity (De Loecker et al., 2020). The idealized labor market depicted in classical theory often contrasts with the realities observed in many countries, including Indonesia. Labor market imperfections, such as market concentration and the monopsony power of employers, play a significant role in shaping labor outcomes (Robinson, 1933; Autor et al., 2020). Monopsony power can lead to wage disparities and exacerbate discriminatory practices, particularly against marginalized worker groups (Kahn & Tracy, 2024). High levels of market concentration amplify monopsony power, thereby granting employers increased control over wages and employment conditions (Kim et al., 2021).

In the context of labor market imperfections, labor regulations, including minimum wage policies, play a crucial role in enhancing workers' bargaining power. Krueger and Posner (2018) suggest reassessing labor regulations to bolster workers' negotiation capabilities, especially through the establishment of minimum wage policies. A minimum wage helps correct disparities by ensuring that low-wage workers earn compensation sufficient to meet a basic standard of living (Wang, 2022). The groundbreaking research by Card and Krueger (1994) questioned the classical theory, which argues that increases in the minimum wage result in job losses due to higher labor costs. Instead, their results indicate that raising the minimum wage may actually boost employment levels in specific regions. This phenomenon can be explained by the presence of monopsony power in labor markets, where a binding minimum wage can raise wages without reducing employment. In some instances, minimum wage policies may even stimulate higher employment rates (Winters, 2022; Neumark & Yen, 2023). The historical foundation of minimum wage policy is rooted in the principle of justice (Rawls, 1971), with the aim of protecting workers from excessively low wages. The International Labour Organization (ILO) asserts that minimum wages ensure workers receive a fair share of economic progress and equitable compensation. These policies also contribute to poverty alleviation and inequality reduction, with over 90 percent of the ILO's 187 member countries implementing some form of minimum wage regulation. Table 2 shows that in 2022, Indonesia's national minimum wage was approximately USD 180.46 per month, ranking 88th globally and fourth within the ASEAN region. This rate was lower than those in Malaysia, Thailand, and Cambodia (ILO, 2023).

Table 1 - Comparison of National Minimum Wage in ASEAN Countries in 2022

Rank		Country	National Minimum Wage (USD)	Comparison to Indonesia
World	ASEAN			
58	1	Malaysia	340.83	1.89
71	2	Thailand	248.42	1.38
83	3	Cambodia	194.00	1.08
88	4	Indonesia	180.46	1.00
92	5	Vietnam	167.40	0.93
96	6	Philippines	147.95	0.82
108	7	Timor-Leste	115.00	0.64
115	8	Laos	85.50	0.47
117	9	Myanmar	70.20	0.39

Source: ILO, 2023 (processed).

In Indonesia, the minimum wage policy is governed by a range of legal provisions aimed at safeguarding workers' rights and maintaining social stability. As outlined in Government Regulation No. 36 of 2021, Article 23 (1), the minimum wage refers to the minimum monthly salary that employers must pay to their workers or employees, as stipulated by existing regulations, employment contracts, or agreements between the employer and the worker. Furthermore, the Job Creation Law (Law No. 6 of 2023) sets additional guidelines for determining the minimum wage, which is decided by provincial governments based on recommendations from the Wage Council, taking into account the local economic and labor conditions. Employers who fail to comply with the established minimum wage may face administrative sanctions, including fines and the suspension of business operations.

This policy also has a profound impact on the conditions of low-wage workers. Recent studies define low-wage workers as those earning below the minimum wage set by law in their respective regions (Redmond & McGuinness, 2025; Zipperer, 2022; Jardim et al., 2022; Godoey & Reich, 2021; Yang & Gunderson, 2020; Bossler & Gerner, 2020; Wong, 2019). This research adopts the same definition, considering low-wage workers as individuals whose earnings fall below the government-mandated minimum wage. Although many regulations related to minimum wage policies have been established, every year there is always controversy surrounding this policy. This controversy arises due to concerns that not all workers receive the minimum wage and that the set amount may not be sufficient to improve workers' welfare, leading to demonstrations. Data from BPS-Statistics Indonesia (BPS) reveals that the number of low-wage workers grew from 80.46 million people in 2020 to 82.60 million people in 2023. However, the proportion decreased from 62.64 percent in 2020 to 59.06 percent in 2023 (see Figure 1). During this period, the average number of hours worked by low-wage workers was 37.97 hours per week, considerably fewer than the 44.67 hours worked by non-low-wage workers. In terms of real wages, the disparity is stark: low-wage workers earned an average of IDR 1.28 million per month, well below the IDR 4.10 million earned by non-low-wage workers (BPS, 2023). These data highlight the urgent need for more effective policy interventions to address the welfare challenges faced by low-wage workers in Indonesia.

Source: BPS, 2023 (processed).

Figure 1 - Trend of the Number and Proportion of Low-Wage Workers in Indonesia

Research on minimum wage policy in Indonesia reveals a variety of significant findings regarding its impact on social welfare and inequality. In terms of household welfare, Hasanah et al. (2024) found that increases in the minimum wage help reduce food insecurity among households with formal sector workers. Abdul (2024) noted that the minimum wage policy could play a role in reducing gender inequality and addressing social disparities. However, Simamora and Widyawati (2022) argued that increases in the minimum wage might actually worsen the gender wage gap, especially at the lower end of the wage spectrum, due to a compression effect that tends to favor men. Noviana (2020) supported the idea that minimum wage policies can reduce income inequality, yet Yamada (2016) pointed out their limitations, stating that these policies may not significantly improve household welfare or overall inequality. Regarding education, Pritadrajati (2021) observed that higher minimum wages could reduce educational investment by incentivizing individuals to leave school earlier, although a positive response was observed among low-income households.

Moreover, minimum wage policy plays a crucial role in shaping labor market dynamics and influencing sectoral productivity. Siregar (2022) observed that rises in the minimum wage affect both formal and informal labor market dynamics, generating spillover effects in neighboring regions, although they do not directly impact labor force participation rates. Similar findings were reported by Higashikata (2021), who highlighted the policy's effect on job creation in the manufacturing sector in West Java, and by Siregar (2020), who found that raising the minimum wage could lead to a reduction in formal employment and an increase in unemployment. In the informal sector, Nafiah (2020) and Pratomo (2016) identified that higher minimum wages tend to push less-educated and low-skilled youth into informal jobs. Meanwhile, Kim and Williams (2021) observed a decrease in bargaining power among low-educated women in the informal labor market. Regarding productivity, Hamzah et al. (2021) found that minimum wage policies have the potential to boost firm productivity, especially for companies that are already paying wages above the minimum required level. Similarly, Agusalm and Novianti (2023) also found an increase in labor productivity. In contrast, Ni and Kurita (2020) found that higher minimum wages may reduce both employment and productivity, although these effects can be mitigated by increased export opportunities. Additionally, Islami and Anis (2019) and Hohberg and Lay (2015) documented spillover effects on poverty levels, while Mutaqin and Huda (2021) showed that interprovincial variations in construction worker wages align with differences in minimum wage levels, underscoring the substantial influence of minimum wage policy on national wage structures. From various studies conducted in Indonesia, there is still a limited number of analyses that link the impact on hours worked and real wages across sectors, gender, and regions, thus requiring comprehensive examination.

In parallel with the expanding body of research on minimum wage policies in different countries, many international studies have explored the effects of these policies on the hours worked and real wages of low-wage workers. Key examples include Redmond and McGuinness (2025) in Ireland, Dütsch et al. (2023) in Germany, Zipperer (2022), Jardim et al. (2022) in Seattle, Godoey and Reich (2021), Clemens and Wither (2019) in the United States, Yang and Gunderson (2020) in China, and Wong (2019) in Ecuador. Although there are many related studies, there has been no specific research in Indonesia that analyzes this matter.

The phenomenon gaps identified in this study can be summarized as follows: (1) Indonesia's minimum wage ranks fourth in ASEAN, with a gap nearly double that of Malaysia's minimum wage; (2) the number of low-wage workers in Indonesia has increased significantly, with 82.60 million people, representing 59.06 percent of the total workforce; (3) the hours worked of low-wage workers are shorter compared to non-low-wage workers; and (4) there is a significant wage gap between low-wage workers and non-low-wage workers.

Considering the existing gaps in both phenomena and prior research, the researcher believes there is still a gap in the study of the impact of the provincial minimum wage (PMW) policy on the hours worked and real wages of low-wage workers. Therefore, this study will contribute to filling this gap by enriching the analysis of the heterogeneous effects of the minimum wage policy on the hours worked and real wages of low-wage workers across sectors, gender, and regions.

This paper consists of five main sections. Section 1 is the introduction, covering the background, phenomena and research gaps, objectives, and contributions of the study. Section 2 presents the literature review, exploring the philosophical reasons behind minimum wage policy and the debates surrounding it. Section 3 outlines the research methodology, including the research design, variables, and analytical techniques. Section 4 presents the results and discussion, including descriptive statistics, PSM balance tests, correlation analyses, heterogeneous effects of minimum wage on hours worked and real wages, robustness tests, and policy implications. Section 5 concludes the paper by summarizing the main findings, offering recommendations, acknowledging the study's limitations, and suggesting directions for future research.

2. Literature review

2.1. Philosophical reasons for minimum wage policy

Minimum wage policy is grounded in a variety of philosophical principles that encompass economic, social, and moral dimensions, collectively providing a strong justification for its implementation. First, minimum wage policy emerged as a response to the inherent imperfections within the labor market, which are clearly observed in economic practice (Robinson, 1933; Bachmann & Frings, 2017; Dobbelaere et al., 2024). In reality, the labor market does not always operate optimally due to various market failures, such as information asymmetry, monopsony, barriers to worker mobility, and imbalances in bargaining power between workers and employers. These conditions often result in workers, particularly in low-wage sectors, receiving compensation that falls below a decent standard of living or being subjected to inhumane working conditions (Rosiński, 2021). In such contexts, government intervention through the establishment of a minimum wage becomes a vital tool to rectify structural injustices and protect workers from exploitation (Neumark & Wascher, 2008; LeBaron, 2021). The implementation of a minimum wage serves as a standard for fair compensation, while also helping to reduce economic inequalities caused by market imperfections. Borjas (2024) supports this notion, arguing that minimum wages provide essential protection for workers who are most susceptible to exploitation in imperfect labor markets. In addition to shielding workers from exploitation, the introduction of a minimum wage acts as a corrective mechanism in the market, potentially improving welfare and ensuring justice for the most vulnerable worker groups.

Second, from the perspective of economic justice, the minimum wage policy is instrumental in promoting a more equitable income distribution and fostering inclusive economic growth. Keynesian theory posits that raising the minimum wage can increase the purchasing power of low-wage workers, thereby stimulating aggregate consumption and driving economic growth (Keynes, 1936). Building on this, Kaleckian theory highlights the redistributive effects of the minimum wage, suggesting that by transferring income from high-wage to low-wage groups, wage inequality can be reduced, and stimulate growth through increased consumption among workers (Kalecki, 1971; 2003). However, the effectiveness of this mechanism is highly contingent upon the labor market's capacity and the economy's production capacity to absorb the rise in demand. In their analysis,

Steiner et al. (2020) discovered that the minimum wage acts as a protective tool for workers, ensuring that full-time employees are not pushed into poverty.

Third, the minimum wage policy extends beyond economic considerations to address broader social justice issues, aiming to mitigate economic disparities arising from an uneven market structure. Simonin et al. (2022) contend that the minimum wage functions as a corrective mechanism for income inequality, particularly benefiting workers in the informal and low-wage sectors. This perspective aligns with the theory of justice proposed by Rawls (1971), especially the difference principle, which asserts that social and economic inequalities can only be justified if they benefit the least advantaged groups in society. In this context, the minimum wage policy can be seen as the practical implementation of this principle, providing wage protection for low-wage workers to enhance their socioeconomic standing. Rawls further argued that, alongside the difference principle, social justice must adhere to the principle of liberty, which guarantees that every individual is entitled to the same basic rights. However, in cases of unavoidable inequality, policy should prioritize improving the well-being of the most vulnerable groups. By establishing a minimum compensation threshold, the minimum wage policy seeks to mitigate inequalities, reinforce distributive justice, and improve the well-being of workers in the most precarious economic positions.

Fourth, from a moral standpoint, the minimum wage policy represents an expression of collective ethical responsibility within society, particularly toward vulnerable groups. Sandel (2010) argues that justice in economic policy not only depends on procedural fairness or the distribution of resources but also involves respect for human dignity and consideration of moral and social values. Building on this notion, the minimum wage policy should be viewed as an instrument to ensure that economic decisions are not only efficient but also substantively just, protecting workers from exploitation, guaranteeing fair compensation, and upholding social justice by respecting the basic rights of every individual. Elvardi et al. (2021) emphasize that allowing individuals to work yet live in unlivable conditions represents a serious moral failure. Within this framework, the introduction of the minimum wage is not simply an economic measure but also a reflection of the state's dedication to ensuring a dignified life for all its citizens. This policy emphasizes the significance of the principle of social solidarity, where collective welfare becomes the central focus in the formulation of economic policies.

This philosophical perspective reinforces the case for raising the minimum wage, viewing it not only as an economic and social requirement but also as a moral obligation that embodies society's collective commitment to preserving the dignity of all workers. Proper adjustments to the minimum wage have the potential to greatly enhance the living standards of low-income households. Moreover, the minimum wage serves as a tool for social justice, as evidenced by the fact that 90 percent of ILO member countries have implemented a minimum wage system. It can protect low-wage workers from substantial loss of purchasing power during periods of high inflation. However, for this mechanism to be effective, the minimum wage must be regularly adjusted, considering the needs of workers and their families as well as prevailing economic conditions. This adjustment process should involve full participation from social partners and incorporate evidence-based social dialogue (ILO, 2023).

2.2. Debates surrounding minimum wage policy

The minimum wage policy is a contentious issue, with two main groups offering opposing views: supporters and critics. Advocates of the minimum wage argue for the necessity of state intervention

to correct injustices within the labor market. From a Keynesian viewpoint, raising the minimum wage is believed to enhance workers' purchasing power, stimulate domestic consumption, and accelerate economic growth through increased aggregate demand (Keynes, 1936). The Kaleckian theory further posits that a more equitable income distribution, including through minimum wage policies, is crucial for maintaining macroeconomic stability (Kalecki, 1971; 2003). This viewpoint is reinforced by the landmark study conducted by Card and Krueger (1994), which showed that raising the minimum wage can lead to increased employment in specific sectors, notably in the fast food industry in New Jersey. This finding challenges the assumption that minimum wage increases necessarily lead to job losses. Their research, which ultimately played a role in earning them a Nobel Prize, represented a pivotal shift in economists' understanding of the relationship between the minimum wage and employment.

Recent empirical studies provide compelling evidence supporting the effectiveness of minimum wage policies. Engbom and Moser (2022) conducted research in Brazil, confirming that adjustments to the minimum wage are effective in reducing income inequality, highlighting the significance of this policy in developing economies. Zipperer (2022) found that raising the minimum wage boosts the income of low-wage workers through mechanisms such as reduced turnover, moderate increases in the prices of goods and services, and the redistribution of workers to more productive firms. A similar study by Godoey and Reich (2021) in the United States supports these findings, showing that increases in the minimum wage in low-wage regions raise income without reducing employment or hours worked, and significantly lower poverty rates. Wong (2019), using a Difference-in-Differences (DID) analysis of data from low-wage workers in Ecuador, demonstrated that a one-percent increase in the minimum wage results in a 0.41–0.48 percent rise in workers' income. While the effects vary by gender and age, these results underline the minimum wage's role in enhancing economic well-being.

Furthermore, several studies contribute to a deeper understanding of the benefits of minimum wage policy. Gabriel and Schmitz (2023) found that increasing the minimum wage helps narrow the racial wage gap in the United States, thereby improving the economic standing of marginalized groups. Hurst et al. (2022) demonstrated that a rise in the minimum wage leads to an increase in workers' income in the short term, while Kuroki (2022) highlighted its strong redistributive effects in reducing income inequality. Dustmann et al. (2022) revealed that the introduction of the minimum wage in Germany effectively increased workers' income without harming employment levels. Clemens and Strain (2021) stressed the need to account for the magnitude of minimum wage increases but generally concluded that their effects have been more beneficial in the past decade. Dubé and Lindner (2021) found that higher minimum wages help reduce turnover rates, leading to greater labor market stability. In Australia, Bishop (2018) showed that an increase in the minimum wage resulted in a significant rise in wage elasticity, without adversely affecting hours worked or unemployment.

Opponents of the minimum wage policy typically ground their arguments in classical and neoclassical economic theories, which stress the importance of market forces in determining labor prices (Smith, 1776). From this viewpoint, government intervention through the establishment of a minimum wage is seen as disrupting the equilibrium between labor demand and supply, potentially resulting in structural unemployment, especially in low-wage sectors (Kim & Lim, 2018; Borjas, 2024). When the minimum wage is set above the market equilibrium, employers may find it difficult or undesirable to hire as many workers, leading to an increased risk of unemployment, particularly among low-skilled workers or first-time job seekers (Garcia-Louzao & Tarasonis, 2021). Furthermore, Benton (2021) points to several studies indicating that raising the minimum wage could have a negative impact on employment levels, although some argue that it may help

reduce poverty without significantly affecting hiring. The corporate response to the minimum wage policy has also been a point of concern, with Wang et al. (2025) noting that some companies reduce their engagement in social responsibility initiatives as a way to adjust to the additional costs. Meanwhile, Sefil-Tansever and Yilmaz (2024) demonstrate the existence of spillover effects, where companies raise wages more broadly to maintain internal hierarchies, which can influence the overall labor market structure.

Several further empirical studies have shown the impact of minimum wage policies on hours worked and labor quality. Mitre-Becerril and Chalfin (2021) observed that the implementation of the minimum wage policy in Seattle led to an increase in the hourly earnings of low-wage workers, but it also resulted in a decrease in hours worked. These outcomes align with concerns highlighted by Maroto and Pettinicchio (2023), who argued that excessively high minimum wages might prompt employers to cut hours worked, limit hiring, or cease recruiting new employees altogether. This pattern indicates that, although the primary goal of raising the minimum wage is to improve the financial well-being of workers, it can have unintended consequences that might offset the expected economic advantages, especially for low-wage employees.

Experiences from different countries also contribute to a deeper understanding of the negative effects of minimum wage policies on the labor market. Bossler and Gerner (2020), in their analysis of the implementation of the national minimum wage in Germany in 2015, found that while average wages increased by 3.8 to 6.3 percent, there was a 1.7 percent decline in employment in affected companies. This reduction was primarily due to decreased new hiring, rather than an increase in layoffs, with labor demand elasticity to wages ranging from -0.2 to -0.4. Clemens and Wither (2019) discovered that during the Great Recession in the United States, raising the federal minimum wage resulted in a substantial decrease in the employment rate for low-wage workers, with an elasticity of -1. Furthermore, this wage increase had an adverse effect on the monthly earnings of low-wage workers, primarily due to a reduction in hours worked, which ultimately hindered the policy's intended objective of enhancing welfare.

Beyond the debate between supporters and opponents of minimum wage policies, the impact of such policies on low-wage workers are multifaceted. Redmond and McGuinness (2025) discovered that in Ireland, although increasing the minimum wage raised workers' incomes, it also resulted in fewer hours worked, particularly in the industrial and accommodation sectors, which could lead to a decrease in overall earnings. On the other hand, Yang and Gunderson (2020) found in China that while the minimum wage increase improved earnings for low-wage workers, especially men, it also caused a decline in job opportunities for women, who did not gain the same benefits from additional pay through longer hours worked. Research by Katzkowicz et al. (2021) in Uruguay also revealed mixed results. While the policy successfully raised wages for formal domestic workers, it also encouraged workers, particularly the youth and those in large cities, to move to the informal sector, potentially jeopardizing job stability. Additionally, a study by Jardim et al. (2022) in Seattle, United States, found that while the minimum wage increase raised hourly wages, it also led to a reduction in hours worked, particularly after the second wage increase, which ultimately lowered the total earnings of low-wage workers.

The view that reducing working hours is detrimental is refuted by Laker & Roulet (2019), who state that reducing working hours can enhance well-being, productivity, and job satisfaction by providing more time for personal activities, family, and rest, which in turn improves work-life balance and mental and physical health. Research by Barp et al. (2024) also indicates that reducing working hours can alleviate fatigue and work-related stress, thereby improving efficiency and work capacity.

Similar findings are presented by Emami et al. (2024), who suggest that flexible working hours can boost productivity through better work-life balance.

3. Research method

3.1. Research design

This study employs a quantitative research design that utilizes secondary data, primarily sourced from BPS-Statistics Indonesia (BPS), the Ministry of Manpower of the Republic of Indonesia, and the International Labour Organization (ILO). The data includes information on Provincial Minimum Wages (PMW), the National Labour Force Survey (*Survei Angkatan Kerja Nasional/Sakernas*), a repeated cross-sectional dataset covering annual data from August 2018 to August 2023, as well as macroeconomic indicators, such as the open unemployment rate and the economic growth rate. This dataset provides an overview of changes and trends over the specified period. It encompasses both micro-level data (at the individual worker level) and macro-level data (across 34 provinces in Indonesia), enabling a comprehensive analysis of variations among different population groups and geographical regions.

3.2. Variables

There are several stages that must be undertaken before estimating the effects using a fully flexible DID model. In the first stage, the dependent variables are constructed, namely weekly hours worked and real monthly wages, with the latter adjusted for inflation to obtain the real values. To address the issue of outliers, both weekly hours worked and real monthly wages are transformed into logarithmic form. In the second stage, the period during which the PMW policy changed is determined. For this study, the years 2020 and 2021 are considered the pre-policy change period, as there were no changes in the PMW policy during these years. The years 2022 and 2023 are designated as the post-policy change period.

In the third stage, treatment and control groups are identified. The treatment group consists of workers whose real wages are between 0.5 times the real PMW of 2022 and below the real PMW of 2023. The control group comprises workers earning between the real PMW of 2023 and 1.5 times the real PMW of 2023. This cutoff is chosen to ensure the analysis remains relevant, as workers with excessively low or high wages could introduce bias. Workers with very low wages may be in unstable conditions or excluded from the formal labor market, while those with significantly higher wages may no longer represent low-wage workers, thus distorting the control group results. By establishing a clear yet adaptable boundary, the study seeks to generate a more representative sample that accurately captures the effects of the PMW policy on low-wage workers. Both the treatment and control groups are confined to formal sector workers who are directly impacted by the PMW policy.

In the fourth stage, the treatment and control groups are matched to be identical in order to avoid selection bias. an appropriate control group for minimum wage studies involves balancing several factors. Choosing a control group with higher wages can reduce the likelihood of spillover effects from minimum wage changes, but as the wage level rises, the control group becomes less comparable to the treatment group. To overcome this challenge, Propensity Score Matching (PSM) using the nearest neighbor method is applied to pair individuals in the treatment group with those in the control group based on the closest propensity scores (Hartarto & Wardani, 2023). This

approach helps address both concerns by ensuring that control group participants are not directly impacted by the minimum wage adjustment, matching workers based on socio-demographic characteristics.

In the fifth stage, independent variables are created, which include a treatment dummy to distinguish between the treatment and control groups, a time dummy to account for time-fixed effects, and the interaction of both to capture specific changes in the treatment group before and after the minimum wage increase. This method enables the isolation of the policy effect from other influencing factors. In the sixth stage, control variables are established to ensure that any differences in weekly hours worked and real wages between the treatment and control groups are genuinely due to changes in the minimum wage, rather than socio-demographic factors. This approach offers a more precise understanding of the impact of the minimum wage policy. The control variables consist of the logarithm of age, along with a set of dummy variables for gender, marital status, education level, worker skills, service sector, and region. Additionally, macroeconomic control variables such as the unemployment rate and economic growth rate are included. The final stage involves performing the estimation using the fully flexible DID method.

3.3. Fully flexible DID model

The fully flexible DID method offers a more adaptive approach compared to conventional DID models. This study adopts the DID approach used in the empirical research by Redmond and McGuinness (2025), which was originally proposed by Mora and Reggio (2015, 2019). In contrast to basic DID models, the fully flexible method does not assume parallel pre-treatment trends. Instead, it permits variations in both the slope and intercept across the entire period, before and after the policy implementation, for both the treatment and control groups. Mora and Reggio (2019) also suggest testing for common trends to ensure that the treatment and control groups display similar patterns of change before the policy, even if these trends are not perfectly parallel. Furthermore, the flexibility of this model allows for a more nuanced analysis of changes in hours worked dynamics across multiple years following the policy intervention.

Formally, the fully flexible DID method is implemented through the regression specified in Equation (1) below:

$$E(Y_{it}|D_i, X_i) = \delta + X'_{it}\beta + \sum_{\tau=t_2}^T \delta_{\tau} I_{\tau}^t + \gamma^D D_i + \sum_{\tau=t_2}^T \alpha_{\tau} I_{\tau}^t * D_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

The outcome variable, Y_{it} represents either the logarithm of weekly hours worked or real monthly wages for worker i in year t . The variable I_{τ}^t is a year-specific dummy variable for year τ . The subscript $\tau = t_2$ refers to the year 2021, which serves as the second year in the pre-treatment period. Therefore, $\tau = t_2$ aids in assessing the changes occurring from two years before the policy intervention through the post-treatment years. The variable D_i is a treatment dummy that equals one for individuals in the treatment group and zero for those in the control group. The interaction term, $I_{\tau}^t * D_i$ captures the specific effect of the treatment over time by interacting year dummies with the treatment dummy. The vector X'_{it} represents a set of sociodemographic control variables, including the log of age and a series of dummy variables for gender, marital status, education level, skill level, industrial sector, service sector, and geographic region. Additionally, this empirical model includes macroeconomic control variables such as the open unemployment rate and the economic growth. Equation (1) is referred to as a fully flexible model because each year dummy is interacted with the treatment dummy. This specification enables the analysis to account for multiple years

before and after the treatment, providing a dynamic view of policy impacts over time. Here, δ denotes the intercept that captures common time effects applied across all periods, β represents the coefficients for sociodemographic and macroeconomic control variables, δ_τ denotes the coefficients for year-specific time effects, γ^D captures the effect of the treatment dummy, α_τ are the coefficients for the interaction terms between year and treatment dummies, and ε_{it} is the error term.

This study also re-estimates Equation (1) by disaggregating the analysis based on economic sector, gender, and region. In the final part of the analysis, a robustness check is performed by redefining the treatment group. Specifically, the treatment group is redefined as workers earning a real wage between 0.5 times and just below the 2023 real PMW, while the control group consists of workers earning between the 2023 real PMW and 1.5 times that amount.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Descriptive analysis, PSM balance test, and correlation

Table 2 presents descriptive statistics comparing the treatment and control groups across two periods - before the PMW policy change (2020–2021) and after the policy adjustment (2022–2023). The treatment group is generally composed of younger workers with lower education and skill levels, and a greater concentration in the service sector and urban areas. In contrast, the control group is generally older, more highly educated, and possesses better skill levels. Additionally, of the treatment group are consistently lower compared to those of the control group.

Table 2 - Descriptive Statistics for Treatment and Control Groups

Variables	Treatment Group		Control Group	
	2020-2021	2022-2023	2020-2021	2022-2023
Weekly hours worked	42.74	44.77	42.65	45.38
Monthly real wages (million IDR)	1.90	1.98	3.01	3.06
Age (years)	35.61	35.66	37.95	37.77
Male (%)	68.18	67.27	69.92	70.64
Married (%)	65.46	63.81	75.84	74.21
High education (%)	18.2	17.84	31.94	30.44
Skilled (%)	23.54	23.37	29.40	28.48
Services sector (%)	61.51	62.67	59.19	58.96
Urban (%)	55.73	58.80	57.85	62.98
Java island (%)	33.14	29.58	37.15	35.40
Observations	94,411	103,641	79,405	89,790

Source: Sakernas, 2018–2023 (processed).

The balance test using the PSM method indicates that the matching procedure successfully improved the comparability between the treatment and control groups. Before matching, there were considerable differences in the characteristics of the two groups, which could have led to bias. However, after using the Nearest Neighbor matching technique, these differences were significantly diminished, making the characteristics of the two groups more alike (see Figure 2), suggesting that PSM effectively minimized imbalances across covariates, thereby enhancing the validity of the analysis. This matching process is crucial to ensure that the outcomes observed in the treatment group are comparable to those in the control group. It allows for a more accurate

evaluation of the causal relationship between the treatment and the outcomes (Hartarto & Wardani, 2023). With the characteristics of the groups more balanced, the observed differences in outcomes are more likely to be attributed to the treatment rather than to pre-existing disparities between the groups.

Figure 2 - PSM Balance Test Results

Subsequently, based on Table 3, the correlation among the independent variables indicates that no correlation exceeds the threshold of 0.8. This suggests that multicollinearity is not a significant issue in the model (Egessa et al., 2021). Therefore, it can be concluded that the model is free from multicollinearity, ensuring the validity of the estimation results. Consequently, the analysis can proceed to the next stage, which involves estimating the fully flexible DID model.

Table 3 - Correlation of Independent Variables

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)	(7)	(8)	(9)	(10)
Log age (1)	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Male (2)	0.095	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Married (3)	0.551	0.114	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Higher education (4)	0.017	-0.316	-0.001	1.000	-	-	-	-	-	-
Skilled (5)	0.114	-0.152	0.109	0.352	1.000	-	-	-	-	-
Services sector (6)	-0.039	-0.193	-0.059	0.372	0.013	1.000	-	-	-	-
Urban (7)	-0.029	-0.063	-0.101	0.038	-0.190	0.164	1.000	-	-	-
Java Island (8)	-0.085	-0.055	-0.106	-0.164	-0.219	-0.050	0.222	1.000	-	-
Unemployment rate (9)	-0.014	-0.012	-0.036	-0.058	-0.092	0.009	0.184	0.426	1.000	-
Growth (10)	0.017	-0.007	0.003	0.039	0.027	0.045	-0.020	-0.094	-0.367	1.000

Source: Author's calculations.

4.2. Heterogeneous effects of minimum wage on hours worked and real wages

The DID estimation results, presented in Table 4, indicate that Models 1-3 for hours worked and Models 4-5 for real wages satisfy the common trend assumption, as required by Mora and Reggio (2019), as evidenced by the insignificant pre-dynamics probability values (p -value > 0.05). The DID results for Model 3 show that the PMW policy has a significant negative effect on hours worked. In 2022 (DID-2022), the coefficient is -0.0097 with a standard error of 0.0033, significant at the 5

percent level. This coefficient suggests that the PMW policy reduces the average hours worked by the treatment group by 0.97 percent reduction in the average hours worked by the treatment group compared to the control group in 2022. In 2023 (DID-2023), the effect intensifies, with the treatment group's hours worked decreasing by an average of 2.91 percent relative to the control group. The increased negative effect from 2022 to 2023 suggests that the PMW policy has a stronger cumulative or long-term effect on reducing hours worked. These findings are consistent with previous research documenting similar effects, such as Dreepaul-Dabee and Tandrayen-Ragoobur (2022) in Mauritius, Gindling and Terrell (2007) in Costa Rica, Jardim et al. (2022) in Seattle, USA, Redmond and McGuinness (2025) in Ireland, and Caliendo et al. (2019) in Germany.

Studies conducted by Caliendo et al. (2019) and Burauel et al. (2020) indicate that employers often use strategies to offset the increased labor costs resulting from minimum wage hikes. Additionally, an increase in the minimum wage may encourage employers to substitute labor with capital, such as automation, to reduce reliance on human labor (Redmond & McGuinness, 2025). often see a notable decrease in hours worked. In certain situations, minimum wage policies also affect the reduction of new hires and employee turnover, as employers become more hesitant to hire additional workers, leading to a decrease in the overall number of hours worked (Jardim et al., 2022).

The DID results for Model 6 show that the PMW policy has a significant positive effect on real wages in both 2022 and 2023. In 2022 (DID-2022), the policy increased the average real wage of workers by 0.49 percent compared to the control group. The effect grew slightly in 2023 (DID-2023), with an increase of 0.61 percent. These findings are consistent with the results of Kuroki (2022) in the United States, Engbom and Moser (2022) in Brazil, and Dustmann et al. (2021) in Germany.

Several studies indicate that the implementation of minimum wage policies can increase real wages, particularly in sectors with previously low wages. For instance, Bhorat et al. (2013) found that in South Africa, real wages rose after the implementation of sectoral minimum wages, particularly in areas where wages were below the newly set minimum. Similarly, Aaronson et al. (2020) found that the increase in the minimum wage in the United States resulted in higher real wage growth for low-wage workers. This wage increase narrows the wage distribution gap at the lower end, enhances the real wages of the lowest-paid workers, and strengthens their bargaining power. As a result, it enables workers to negotiate better wages, potentially extending the positive effects on wages to groups beyond those directly impacted (Redmond et al., 2021; Engbom & Moser, 2022). Therefore, the minimum wage policy not only increases nominal wages but also enhances the purchasing power and overall well-being of low-wage workers.

Sociodemographic variables significantly effect changes in hours worked in Model 3. Age has a negative effect, a one percent increase in age leads to a 0.10 percent decrease in average hours worked. Gender is positively related to hours worked, with men tending to work 3.92 percent longer than women. Additionally, married workers work 1.63 percent fewer hours compared to unmarried workers. Higher education levels also show a significant negative effect, with highly educated workers averaging 13.32 percent fewer hours worked compared to those with lower or intermediate education levels. Similarly, skilled workers work 13.27 percent fewer hours compared to unskilled workers. Workers in the service sector also record 6.37 percent fewer hours worked compared to those in the non-service sector. Geographically, workers living in urban areas work 5.35 percent more hours than those in rural areas. Conversely, workers on Java Island work 1.05 percent fewer hours compared to those working outside Java. These sociodemographic effects align with the findings of Yavuz (2021), Amankwah et al. (2022), Jati et al. (2021), and Mia (2025).

Macroeconomic variables also have a notable impact on hours worked. The unemployment rate has a positive effect, where a one percent increase in the unemployment rate results in a 0.27 percent increase in hours worked. On the other hand, the economic growth rate has a negative effect, with a one percent rise in the economic growth rate leading to a 0.19 percent decrease in average hours worked. These findings are consistent with literature suggesting that technological

advancements and productivity improvements within the context of economic growth drive individuals' preferences for more leisure time, thereby reducing the supply of working hours (Irmen, 2018; Epstein & Kimball, 2021).

The analysis of Model 6 also reveals a significant influence of sociodemographic variables on workers' real wages. Age has a positive effect: a one percent increase in age leads to a 0.040 percent increase in real wages. Gender also has a significant effect, with men earning 5.34 percent higher real wages compared to women. Married workers receive 1.60 percent higher real wages compared to unmarried workers. Higher education exerts a substantial effect, with workers possessing higher education earning 8.31 percent higher real wages compared to those with lower or intermediate education levels. Conversely, workers in the service sector earn 0.89 percent lower real wages compared to those in the non-service sector. Geographically, workers living in urban areas earn 3.57 percent higher real wages compared to those in rural areas. However, workers on Java Island have real wages that are 36.41 percent lower compared to those working outside Java. These sociodemographic influences align with the findings of Galván and Aguirre (2025), Vinokurov and Vinokurova (2021), and Katovich and Maia (2018).

Macroeconomic variables also significantly affect real wages. Unemployment rate shows a positive effect, where a one percent increase in the unemployment rate is associated with a 0.04 percent increase in real wages. Similarly, the economic growth shows a positive effect, with a one percent increase in economic growth leading to a 0.01 percent increase in real wages. These findings are consistent with literature suggesting that economic growth enhances labor productivity, which, in turn, drives increases in real wages without proportionally raising labor costs (Ericsson & Molinder, 2020; Irmen, 2025).

Table 4 – The Effect of PMW on Hours Worked and Real Wages

Variables	Log Hours Worked			Log Real Wages		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
DID estimates						
DID-2022	-0.0160*** (0.0036)	-0.0095** (0.0033)	-0.0097** (0.0033)	0.0146*** (0.0029)	0.0063** (0.0024)	0.0049** (0.0023)
DID-2023	-0.0414*** (0.0037)	-0.0285*** (0.0034)	-0.0291*** (0.0034)	0.0137*** (0.0029)	0.0108*** (0.0024)	0.0061*** (0.0023)
Sociodemographic var.						
Log age	-	-0.1047*** (0.0024)	-0.1047*** (0.0024)	-	0.0441*** (0.0017)	0.0406*** (0.0016)
Male	-	0.0393*** (0.0014)	0.0392*** (0.0014)	-	0.0565*** (0.0011)	0.0534*** (0.0010)
Married	-	-0.0164*** (0.0016)	-0.0163*** (0.0016)	-	0.0144*** (0.0012)	0.0160*** (0.0011)
Higher education	-	-0.1339*** (0.0018)	-0.1332*** (0.0018)	-	0.0796*** (0.0013)	0.0831*** (0.0013)
Skilled	-	-0.1325*** (0.0017)	-0.1327*** (0.0017)	-	0.0012 (0.0011)	0.0018 (0.0011)
Services sector	-	-0.0640*** (0.0013)	-0.0637*** (0.0013)	-	-0.0051*** (0.0010)	-0.0089*** (0.0010)
Urban	-	0.0551*** (0.0013)	0.0535*** (0.0013)	-	0.0492*** (0.0008)	0.0357*** (0.0008)
Java Island	-	-0.0059*** (0.0013)	-0.0105*** (0.0014)	-	-0.3075*** (0.0011)	-0.3641*** (0.0010)
Macroeconomic var.						
Unemployment rate	-	-	0.0027*** (0.0004)	-	-	0.0450*** (0.0003)
Growth	-	-	-0.0019*** (0.0003)	-	-	0.0098*** (0.0002)
Constant	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time fixed effect	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes

Variables	Log Hours Worked			Log Real Wages		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
DID estimates						
Pre-dynamics: <i>p</i> -value	0.1119	0.2454	0.2525	0.3195	0.1278	0.7463
Observations		367,247			367,247	

Notes: Model 1 and Model 4 are the baseline models without including sociodemographic and macroeconomic control variables. Model 2 and Model 5 expand the baseline models by incorporating sociodemographic control variables. Model 3 and Model 6 represent the main model specifications developed from the baseline models, incorporating both sociodemographic and macroeconomic control variables. Robust standard errors are presented in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

The DID estimation results in Table 5 show that the impact of the PMW policy on hours worked and real wages differs across economic sectors, gender, and regions. This analysis emphasizes groups with significant coefficients and those that meet the assumption of common trend dynamics before the minimum wage increase, as indicated by the pre-dynamics *p*-value exceeding 0.05 (Mora & Reggio, 2019). In terms of sectors, the DID results show that the effect of the PMW policy on hours worked is heterogeneous across the six sectors that meet both the significance criteria and the common trend dynamics assumption, which include agriculture, forestry, and fishing; transportation and storage; business activities; public administration, defense, and compulsory social security; education services; and other services. In the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector, there was a notable rise in hours worked in 2022, indicating a potential adjustment in work intensity to sustain productivity despite higher wages. Similarly, the transportation and storage sector experienced a significant increase in hours worked in both 2022 and 2023, indicating operational pressures resulting from changes in labor costs. In contrast, the business activities sector experienced a significant decrease in hours worked in both years, which may reflect the flexibility of this sector in adjusting workloads in response to the wage policy. In the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector, there was a significant reduction in hours worked in 2023, suggesting that even relatively stable formal sectors are not entirely immune to the effects of this policy. A decrease in hours worked was also observed in the education services sector in both years, aligning with the hypothesis that social service-based sectors are more sensitive to workload adjustments resulting from changes in labor costs. Finally, the other services sector recorded a significant reduction in hours worked in 2023, reinforcing the idea that sectors with relatively low profit margins tend to reduce hours worked as a response to the PMW increase, as supported by the findings of Asmal et al. (2024).

The heterogeneous effect across sectors is driven by the specific labor market characteristics of each sector. In the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector, which is generally more competitive and less regulated, typically react to minimum wage increases by extending hours worked instead of reducing the workforce. This is viewed as a compensation mechanism for lower base productivity and higher work flexibility (Fan & Pena, 2019). In contrast, in more regulated and structured sectors, such as public administration, defense, and compulsory social security, education services, and business activities, minimum wage increases are more commonly associated with a reduction in hours worked. This is due to the presence of formal labor contracts, a strong institutional framework, and the influence of labor unions, which advocate for workload adjustments through shorter hours worked (Redmond & McGuinness, 2025; McGuinness et al., 2019).

Meanwhile, the impact brought by the PMW policy on real wages also shows important sectoral variations. Among the 16 sectors that meet the common trend assumption, marked by a pre-dynamics probability values greater than 0.05, nine sectors did not show a significant impact on real wages. Mahyuddin et al. (2006) explain that this occurs due to wage rigidity, which is the inability of wages to adjust to changes in the labor market. Although the minimum wage policy raises nominal wages, an excess supply of labor in certain sectors restricts the market's capacity to

substantially increase wages. Furthermore, inflation can erode real wages, diminishing workers' purchasing power. Consequently, the minimum wage policy has a limited effect increasing real wages in these sectors.

Seven sectors show significant effects and meet the common trend assumption regarding real wages: trade; accommodation and food services; business activities; public administration, defense, and compulsory social security; social security; education; and human health and social work. A positive effect is observed in the Accommodation and food services, and public administration, defense, and compulsory social security sectors, where the PMW policy significantly increased real wages in 2022, reflecting these sectors' ability to adjust their wage structures in response to the minimum wage policy. Additionally, the education sector also shows a significant increase in real wages in both 2022 and 2023, indicating that workers in this sector consistently benefit from the PMW policy. In contrast, a negative effect on real wages is observed in the trade and other services sectors, which saw a significant decrease in 2022, as well as in the business services sector in 2023. The human health and social work sector also recorded a significant decline in real wages in both years.

The heterogeneous effect reflects the diversity in wage structures, regulation levels, productivity, and the prevalence of informal work across sectors. In low-wage sectors, the minimum wage plays a significant role in increasing workers' income and reducing inequality, as a large proportion of workers earn wages near the minimum threshold. On the other hand, high-wage sectors like technology and finance experience little to no impact, as workers' wages are already significantly higher than the minimum wage (Strawiński & Majchrowska, 2025). Sectoral adherence to the policy is also crucial. Sectors with higher compliance are more likely to undergo structural changes, such as shifts in labor or reductions in inequality. In contrast, sectors with lower compliance tend to show more limited effects or even distortions in the market (Heise & Pusch, 2020). Moreover, the policy can generate spillover effects, where a rise in the minimum wage indirectly boosts wages in related sectors because of the greater demand for skilled labor (Demirtaş, 2022). Furthermore, sectoral responses to the minimum wage policy are influenced by capital intensity and market pressures. Labor-intensive industries tend to increase capital investment to reduce labor costs (Geng et al., 2022), while sectors with limited investment capacity may cut capital spending or resort to layoffs (Gustafson & Kotter, 2023). Additionally, competitive pressures and macroeconomic conditions, such as relative price changes and labor market conditions, shape the policy's effects, with sectors heavily reliant on cheap labor being more vulnerable to negative effects compared to sectors that are more protected (Braun et al., 2020).

By gender, the effect of the PMW policy on hours worked and real wages reveals significant differences between male and female workers. For female workers, the PMW policy consistently reduced hours worked in both 2022 and 2023, with a larger reduction in the second year. This may reflect the policy's greater sensitivity to the work patterns of women, who may be more vulnerable to reductions in hours worked due to changes in minimum wage policies, as found by Asmal et al. (2024). Regarding real wages, significant effects are observed among male workers, where the PMW policy significantly increased real wages in 2023. This suggests that male workers, who are often employed in sectors with higher minimum wages, directly benefit from this policy. In contrast, for female workers, although the common trend assumption is met, there is no notable difference between the treatment and control groups, suggesting that the effect of the PMW policy on real wages for women is not as pronounced as it is for men.

The differences in effect between genders are attributed to variations in job attachment, dominant sectors, and the labor market structure faced by men and women. The rise in the minimum wage

strengthens job attachment for men, given their higher likelihood of working in full-time and formal sectors, which tend to offer more job stability (García-Morán et al., 2024). In contrast, women, who are more concentrated in low-wage and part-time sectors, are more vulnerable to negative adjustments, such as reductions in hours worked, due to the greater sensitivity of these sectors to labor cost increases (Dreepaul-Dabee & Tandrayen-Ragoobur, 2022). This situation is further exacerbated by a high mismatch between desired and actual working hours among women, especially those with domestic responsibilities, thereby reducing their chances of maintaining full hours worked (Beckmannshagen & Schroeder, 2022). As a result, men benefit more from increases in real wages due to their involvement in full-time positions that directly benefit from the minimum wage adjustments (Cho & Yang, 2023). Furthermore, the labor market structure, which tends to favor male workers, reinforces these gains, while women continue to face structural barriers that limit the benefits they receive from the minimum wage policy (Duval-Hernández, 2023).

Geographically, the effect of the PMW policy on hours worked and real wages shows significant differences between urban and rural areas. In urban areas, workers experienced a significant decrease in hours worked in 2023, with the pre-dynamics assumption being met, indicating that the PMW policy played a role in reducing hours worked in urban areas. In contrast, in rural areas saw a significant reduction in hours worked in both 2022 and 2023, indicating that the impact of the PMW policy in rural areas emerged earlier and tends to be more persistent. In terms of real wages, the PMW policy had a positive effect in both urban and rural areas, but with different patterns. In urban areas, a significant increase in real wages occurred in 2022, reflecting more immediate benefits for urban workers. Meanwhile, in rural areas, the positive effect was larger in 2023, indicating that the PMW policy provided greater benefits to rural workers, who generally have lower wage levels compared to their urban counterparts.

Rural areas are more affected due to differences in economic structure, labor market dynamics, and demographic characteristics. Rural areas typically have a higher concentration of low-wage jobs, meaning the minimum wage ratio relative to market wages is larger, leading to more substantial wage increases without necessarily causing a drastic reduction in employment (Godoy & Reich, 2021). In contrast, urban areas, with more diversified economies, are better able to absorb wage increases without significant changes in the employment structure (Fossati & Marchand, 2024). From a labor market perspective, rural areas, which tend to be less flexible, experience more pronounced reductions in working hours when labor costs rise (Kim et al., 2023), exacerbated by stronger spillover effects due to limited local economic linkages (Jardim et al., 2024). Additionally, the demographic characteristics of rural areas, such as a high proportion of vulnerable young workers, make these regions more sensitive to changes in labor policies compared to urban areas, which tend to be more resilient (Fossati & Marchand, 2024).

Table 5 – DID Estimates by Sector, Gender, and Region

Variables	Log Hours Worked			Log Real Wages		
	DID-2022	DID-2023	Pre-dynamics: <i>p</i> -value	DID-2022	DID-2023	Pre-dynamics: <i>p</i> -value
Sector						
Agriculture, forestry, and fishing (N=38,613)	0.0254** (0.0099)	0.0104 (0.0010)	0.0737	0.0025 (0.0063)	0.0076 (0.0061)	0.0707
Mining and quarrying (N=10,769)	0.0132 (0.0186)	0.0014 (0.0195)	0.0428	-0.0085 (0.0119)	0.0107 (0.0123)	0.3921
Manufacturing (N=56,786)	0.0333*** (0.0060)	0.0085 (0.0067)	0.0003	-0.0021 (0.0054)	-0.0013 (0.0057)	0.5855
Electricity and gas (N=2,611)	0.0179 (0.0346)	0.0207 (0.03333)	0.3972	0.0345 (0.0250)	0.0336 (0.0264)	0.1668

Variables	Log Hours Worked			Log Real Wages		
	DID-2022	DID-2023	Pre-dynamics: <i>p</i> -value	DID-2022	DID-2023	Pre-dynamics: <i>p</i> -value
Water supply; sewerage, waste management, and remediation (N=1,530)	-0.2571 (0.0472)	-0.0391 (0.0472)	0.5998	0.0005 (0.0345)	0.0105 (0.0355)	0.6172
Construction (N=33,974)	0.0391*** (0.0086)	0.0279*** (0.0086)	0.0477	-0.0037 (0.0065)	0.0096 (0.0066)	0.0022
Trade (N=48,183)	0.0056 (0.0076)	0.0018 (0.0073)	0.5942	-0.0136** (0.0067)	0.0066 (0.0065)	0.4858
Transportation and storage (N=17,852)	0.0443*** (0.0162)	0.0343** (0.0166)	0.1975	0.0069 (0.0111)	0.0095 (0.0114)	0.6468
Accommodation and food services (N=14,565)	-0.0012 (0.0193)	-0.0029 (0.01873)	0.0098	0.0030** (0.0132)	0.0263 (0.0129)	0.142
Information and communication (N=3,291)	0.0027 (0.0346)	-0.0135 (0.0370)	0.3437	-0.0027 (0.0290)	0.0027 (0.0287)	0.9794
Financial and insurance (N=9,426)	0.0154 (0.015617)	0.0051 (0.0168)	0.6995	0.0052 (0.0151)	-0.0181 (0.0153)	0.9469
Real estate (N=1,024)	0.0293 (0.0478)	0.0358 (0.0516)	0.7306	-0.0175 (0.0604)	0.0480 (0.0605)	0.2806
Business activities (N=8,710)	-0.0549** (0.0229)	-0.0734*** (0.0225)	0.0744	-0.0248 (0.0180)	-0.0453*** (0.0174)	0.6076
Public administration, defense, and compulsory social security (N=50,700)	0.0105 (0.0086)	-0.0165* (0.0090)	0.2655	0.0158*** (0.0060)	-0.0082 (0.0061)	0.5215
Education (N=39,191)	-0.0279** (0.0133)	-0.0474*** (0.0134)	0.154	0.0357*** (0.0070)	0.0243*** (0.0071)	0.4888
Human health and social work (N=15,470)	0.0109 (0.0136)	-0.0124 (0.0141)	0.767	-0.0241** (0.0110)	-0.0264** (0.0115)	0.3301
Other services (N=14,552)	-0.0162 (0.0250)	-0.0658*** (0.02380)	0.1744	-0.0230* (0.0134)	-0.0161 (0.0133)	0.5889
Gender						
Male (N=253,038)	0.0024 (0.0039)	-0.0155*** (0.0040)	0.0237	0.0038 (0.0027)	0.0122*** (0.0027)	0.1662
Female (N=114,209)	-0.0408*** (0.0064)	-0.0653*** (0.0065)	0.1205	0.0062 (0.0042)	-0.0041 (0.0041)	0.1248
Region						
Urban (N=216,038)	-0.0021 (0.0041)	-0.0263*** (0.0042)	0.8668	0.0057* (0.0032)	0.0001 (0.0032)	0.8900
Rural (N=151,209)	-0.0221*** (0.0055)	-0.0370*** (0.0058)	0.0730	0.0047 (0.0030)	0.0145*** (0.0031)	0.8878

Notes: Estimation results are obtained using Model 3 for hours worked and Model 6 for real wages in Table 4, which include sociodemographic and macroeconomic control variables. Robust standard errors are presented in parentheses. *, **, and *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

4.3. Robustness tests

This study is complemented by a robustness test to ensure the consistency of the estimated effect of the PMW policy on hours worked and real wages, despite changes in the definition of the treatment and control groups. The robustness test results, shown in Table 6, indicate that the estimated impact of the PMW policy on hours worked and real wages remains stable across all models, even when the definitions between the two groups are altered. The estimation outcomes display robustness, as reflected not only in the direction of the coefficients and their significance levels but also in the pre-dynamics values, with consistently high *p*-values ($p > 0.05$).

Table 6 - DID Estimates Based on Varying the Threshold of Treatment and Control Group

Variables	Log Hours Worked			Log Real Wages		
	Model 1	Model 2	Model 3	Model 4	Model 5	Model 6
DID-2022	-0.0162*** (0.0036)	-0.0110*** (0.0034)	-0.0112*** (0.0034)	0.0173*** (0.0029)	0.0049*** (0.0024)	0.0053*** (0.0023)
DID-2023	-0.0386*** (0.0037)	-0.0293*** (0.0034)	-0.0297*** (0.0034)	0.0180*** (0.0029)	0.0057*** (0.0024)	0.0022*** (0.0023)
Sociodemographic var.	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	Yes
Macroeconomic var.	No	No	Yes	No	No	Yes
Constant	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Time fixed effects	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Pre-dynamics: p -value	0.1701	0.4225	0.4394	0.7867	0.7889	0.7958
Observations		353,262			353,262	

Notes: The robustness of the model is tested by redefining the treatment groups, specifically workers earning real wages between 0.5 times the real PMW of 2023 and below the real PMW of 2023, while the control group consists of workers earning wages between the real PMW of 2023 and 1.5 times the real PMW of 2023. Robust standard errors are presented in parentheses. *, **, and *** indicate significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% levels, respectively.

The results of this study indicate that while the minimum wage policy can increase real wages, it also results in a decrease in hours worked. In classical economic theory, this decrease in hours worked is explained by labor elasticity, marginal labor efficiency, and technological substitution. If wages exceed the market equilibrium level, firms are likely to reduce labor or hours worked (Mitre-Becerril & Chalfin, 2021; Garcia-Louzao & Tarasonis, 2021). Firms will also reduce hours worked if productivity does not increase (Maroto & Pettinicchio, 2023). From a classical perspective, minimum wage policies are seen as a distortion of the market mechanism, where the market tends to correct itself through a reduction in labor demand (Brall & Schmid, 2023; Lordan, 2019).

In contrast, the Keynesian perspective highlights the beneficial impact of this policy, particularly the rise in workers' purchasing power, which stimulates consumption (Keynes, 1936). The rise in the minimum wage is viewed as an economic stimulus that can support economic growth (Krugman & Wells, 2021; Sefil-Tansever & Yilmaz, 2024). Keynesians also emphasize the importance of wage behavior theory in the long term, suggesting that higher wages can motivate workers to be more productive, increase loyalty, and reduce labor turnover (Jahan & Jabin, 2024; Harmen, 2024). Additionally, this policy can reduce income inequality and improve the well-being of workers, particularly in the formal sector (Rawls, 1971; ILO, 2023). Although there are short-term effects, such as a reduction in hours worked, its long-term effects can contribute to a more stable and healthy labor ecosystem (Bossler & Gerner, 2020).

Beyond the two major perspectives, there is the argument that reducing working hours can be seen as a positive development in terms of work-life balance. Laker & Roulet (2019) contend that reducing working hours can enhance well-being, productivity, and job satisfaction by providing more time for personal activities, family, and rest, which in turn improves work-life balance and contributes to better mental and physical health. Furthermore, reducing working hours allows workers to recover both physically and mentally, which directly impacts holistic well-being. More leisure time not only supports the balance between work and social life but also enhances overall quality of life, leading workers to feel more valued and motivated within their work environment (Barp et al., 2024; Lepinteur, 2019).

Based on the research findings, several strategic policies can be proposed to complement the PMW policy in protecting low-wage workers. First, fiscal incentive policies, such as tax cuts and inclusive technological support, should be introduced for companies that maintain hours worked despite the minimum wage increase or that aim to improve productivity without replacing labor. Additionally, from the workers' side, direct subsidies and income tax relief could help alleviate economic

burdens. Second, strengthening the authority of Regional Wage Councils to set minimum wages based on local indicators would enable more tailored adjustments to reflect regional circumstances. Third, broadening the scope of the minimum wage coverage policy to be sector-specific could address the diverse needs of different industries. Fourth, conducting regular gender-based audits would ensure that wage policies are equitably implemented across gender lines. Fifth, investing in education and skills enhancement through national training programs, coupled with incentives for companies to train their workers, would make the workforce more productive and competitive.

5. Conclusion

The PMW policy exerts differential impacts on workers' hours worked and their real wages. It leads to a decrease in the average hours worked within the treatment group relative to the control group, indicating employers' reactions to the policy. In contrast, the policy results in higher average real wages for workers in the treatment group compared to those in the control group, which aligns with the fundamental objective of implementing a minimum wage. Moreover, the influence of the PMW policy on hours worked and real wages is heterogeneous across sectors, gender, and regions. From a sectoral perspective, the number of hours worked rose in the agriculture, forestry, and fishing sector, in addition to in the transportation and storage sector, while they decreased in business activities, public administration, defense, and compulsory social security, education, and other services. Regarding real wages, increases were noted in the accommodation and food services, public administration, defense, and compulsory social security, and education sectors, whereas decreases were found in trade, business activities, human health and social work, and other services. By gender, women consistently showed a decrease in hours worked without a notable rise in real wages, whereas men experienced an increase in their real wages. Regionally, the decrease in hours worked took place more swiftly in rural areas than in urban ones, whereas increases in real wages were initially observed sooner in urban areas but became more substantial in rural areas after one year. These differences reflect variations in sectoral structure, labor market dynamics, and gender and regional inequalities in responding to the minimum wage policy. Policy recommendations to complement the PMW in protecting low-wage workers include providing fiscal incentives to companies that maintain hours worked, strengthening the authority of Regional Wage Councils, implementing sector-specific minimum wages, conducting gender-based wage audits, and investing in education and skill development for workers. Future research is recommended to explore the interaction between minimum wage policies and social protection programs to better understand their combined effect on worker welfare. This would provide valuable insights for generating more integrated and effective policy recommendations.

This analysis has limitations stemming from the use of self-reported hours worked, which may potentially contain measurement errors and lead to less accurate estimates. Furthermore, although the DID method can control for time-invariant factors, the presence of changing confounders during the post-policy period remains a threat to the validity of identification. However, robustness tests provide additional confidence in the reliability of the main estimation results. In the future, subsequent research could focus on exploring the interaction between minimum wage policies and social protection policies, such as health insurance or job training programs, to understand how the combination of these policies influences labor force participation, hour worked distribution, and real wage dynamics among low-income workers. By considering policy interactions and improving measurement quality, the analysis is expected to provide a more accurate and comprehensive understanding of the policy impacts in the labor market.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declared no potential conflict of interest concerning this article's research, authorship, and/or publication.

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